
Impact of Armed Banditry on Security in Northwest Nigeria: An Overview

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ABSTRACT

Armed banditry activities including kidnapping, armed robbery, attacks on travelers, traders and cattle resulting are the major security challenges facing northwest of Nigeria recently. The main objective of this paper is to investigate the impact of armed banditry on security in Northwest Nigeria. The intensive emerge and outcrop of armed banditry activities and incidence in some northwest states and its negative impact on citizen's life exposed the security defect in the country mainly in Northwest region. The insecurity situation including loss of people lives, properties and general social disorder and instability has shown the inability of security system to combat the banditry as a serious phenomenon. The study used descriptive and exploratory approach to examine armed banditry activities in the area, and secondary source of data is mainly used. The study findings reveals that the main causes of armed banditry in northwest region include weak of security system, wide range of under-governed spaces, proliferation of small arms and light weapons, fragile and weak of border management and socioeconomic conditions such as unemployment, poverty and illegal mining activities. The study also found that armed banditry undermines security, peace and stability of the region as well as the increasing attacks of armed banditries on citizens have led to the destruction of lives and properties. Based on the findings the study recommended that, the strengthening of security system, effectiveness of adequate and modern equipment's for security sectors can prevent the escalation of armed banditry. Also introducing new controlling borders measures to combat the flow of weapons with neighboring states and countries is highly recommended. Moreover, poverty eradications programs and providing more employments opportunities especially for youth will be one of the effective and sustainable strategies for addressing armed banditry and related criminal acts in northwest of the country.

Keywords: Armed banditry, Armed Robbery, Kidnapping, Northwest, Security

INTRODUCTION

Banditry is one of the alarming issues today in north-western region of Nigeria that instigate threat in life of innocent citizens. The proliferation of heavy and lighter weapons in hand of non-security

operatives in Nigeria, leads to insecurity which cause harm, threat, anxiety and fear in life of citizens. The prevalence of these weapons in north-west region of Nigeria, particularly, Kaduna, Katsina, Sokoto and Zamfara state have become nerve-racking to national security. However, it involves the use of force, threat to effect and intimidates a person with the intent to rob rape or kill. Banditry involves the use of power and cause violence in societies. The prevalence of banditry in Nigeria appears to have been high and rising over the years. Security challenges can be traced to the early years of military rule when large quantities of arms were imported into the country for the use of the military during and after the Nigerian civil war, some of which got into the hand of the civilians. Soon after the civil war these arms were used by civilians and ex-military men for mischievous purposes such as armed robbery (Olabanji and Ese 2014). The 1999 constitutions make provisions for the rights of citizens. The inability of government to provide a secure and safe environment for lives, properties and the conduct of business and economic activities has led to resentment and disaffection among business investors. Thus the alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has made the economy unattractive to foreign investors and has slowed down the level of business activities, and this has impacted negatively on economic growth and development. This has resulted communal clashes and religious violence and crime in different part of the country that has destroyed lives and properties, disrupted businesses and economic activities, and retarded economic growth and development in Nigeria. No business investors whether local or foreign t will be motivated to invest in an unsafe and insecure environment. In a globalized world investors are not only looking for high returns on their investments but also safe environment for their investments.

According to Rotberg (2007:33), "crime against persons, including murder, rape, and robbery has grown in scale and viciousness in Nigeria since 1999". This has been demonstrated by the pervasive trend of armed banditry and related criminal activities in the country, which in effect mirrors the Africa-wide experience. In fact, reports of bandits

with sophisticated hardware (weapons) rampaging herder's settlements and farms with the sole aim of killing people and pillaging cows proliferates in northwest of the country recently. According to Ahmađu Sulaiman, chairman of the Kaduna States Miyetti Allah Cattle Breeders Association of Nigeria (MACBA), between October 2013 and March, 2014, approximately 7,000 cattle were rustled from commercial livestock farms and traditional herders in Northern Nigeria" (Bashir, 2014) cited in (Azeez and Aliyu, 2016). The scales of armed bandit's activities have led to high rate of death, injury, loss of properties and displacement of individuals in this part of the country. Based on current insecurity environment that have seen in northwest region which caused by banditry and kidnapping activities, this paper aims to overview the impact of banditry and armed robbery as emerging security threat in northwest part of the country.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive method to established findings on the impact of banditry on security in Northwest Nigeria. This is necessary due to difficulties in quantifying the real impact of banditry activities as posed by high uncertainly, volatility trend and rapidly evolving nature of armed banditry incidents in the area. Data were gathered from secondary sources published sources including academic and professional journals, textbooks, relevant government ministers and agencies. The data generated were analyzed using content analysis. The study focuses on understanding the potential impact of the banditry on security in Northwest Nigeria in order to propose policy recommendations to respond to the crisis.

Theoretical Framework

The study anchored on the Human Needs Theory. Human Needs theory generally proposed that all humans have certain basic universal needs and that whenever these needs are denied, conflict is likely to occur. Conflict, and Peace are interrelated and affect all aspect of human life, academics This theory centrally posits that human beings need certain essentials if they most live and attain some level of well-

being in any ramification of life, and that such essential are what is referred to as (basic) human needs and practitioners have usually addressed them in a rather fragmented manner (John W. Burton, 1990). Hence the position of the human needs theory is that the unavailability of any alternative means to meet the needs of individuals or group is usually what triggers violence or conflict. The theory further argued that often a time, violence also occurs when humans require understanding, respect and consideration for their needs. These needs, as argued by the theory are not only the subsistence such as food, water and shelter but also often the biological needs such as participation, identity, understanding and recognition. Therefore, the main concepts and assumptions of the theory are appropriately provide the explanations of the menace of insecurity environment in north western region of the country which is negatively affected the peoples life and emergence of national security threat. It is on record that the northwest states are now completely ensued with an unending armed bandits associated with kidnapping, armed robbery on highways, attack of travelers and traders. Since the theory also intended to address issues that are violent in nature, it is an unarguable fact that Kaduna, Katsina, Sokoto and Zamfara States are currently grappling with the menace of armed bandits which had generally and negatively affected the regions. In this context the human needs theory is more relevant to guide and explain this study.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Typology of Northwest Region

The Northwest is one of the largest geopolitical zones in Nigeria in terms of landmass and population. The zone covered 192, 689 km equivalent to 83, 415 sq mi of land with a combined population of about 40 million of Nigeria's 200 million people (NBS, 2017). Hausa and Fulani ethnic groups are the predominant groups in the Northwest with minority groups across the geo-political zone. The zone comprises up to seven states of Sokoto, Zamfara, Kebbi, Katsina, Kaduna, Kano, and Jigawa. A significant part of Northwest is dry land, but the land is fertile and agrarian for farming and livestock

development. In spite of the potentials of the Northwest, since the return of democracy the zone has experienced devastating rural and armed banditry which claims thousands of lives and properties. It began as localized disputes between headers and farmers over access to land and water resources. However, poor handling of the rural banditry has significantly contributed to its transformation into a deadly conflict posing a major threat to national and regional security and integration (Anka, 2018). The pattern and intensity of rural banditry in the Northwest are connected to socio-economic, environmental, and political forces which shape the development of the geo-political zone. The first is what could be described as environmental forces caused partly by climatic conditions and changes that the sub-region is faced with (Kuna & Ibrahim, 2015). Likewise, in the same line the combination of socio-economic and political forces contributed to escalate armed banditry in the region.

The Northwest has different points been affected by drought, food insecurity, flooding and shrinking of rivers due to changes in climatic conditions. These changes influenced herders and farmers' movement from one area to another in most cases beyond the zone in search of water resources and grazing land. Where this movement coincides with the harvesting period, it becomes a source of conflicts between farmers and herders with devastating effects on agricultural and livestock development of the Northwest. Farmers and herders who lost their farmlands and products or herders who lost their cattle resort to rural banditry as a means of survival. Added to the growing tension over resources between farmers and herders is a rivalry between self-help groups mostly the Hausas who are deployed by local communities to curtail the insurgency on the one hand and the herders predominantly the Fulanis and who are accused of rural banditry across Nigeria (Olaniyan and Yahaya, 2016).

Empirical evidence shows that some of these lands located in places such as Birnin-Gwari Kaduna, Tureta in Sokoto and Birnin-Magaji in Zamfara state were used for the construction of farm houses and filling

stations. While some of these urban development programmes are desirable, many others were of no relevance to rural development as it only intensified agricultural capitalism for easy access to agricultural facilities and loans from financial institutions (Gupta, 2015). Such kind of these urban extension projects will raise certain problems among communities, despite of the need for urban development programs to minimize unoccupied land spaces and security challenges in Northwest region.

Causes of Armed Banditry in Northwest Nigeria

There are several factors have been addressed by different scholars as the leading factors of armed banditry in Nigeria and most especially in the northwest region of the country. For instance, divers of banditry in northwestern Nigeria consist of some socio-existential conditions that characterize the interior as well as the frontiers of the region. Prominent among these conditions are the scarcely governed, the hinterlands, forestlands and borderlines of the region (Abdulyakeem, 2020). Some of the major cause of armed banditry in Zamfara State as stated by Cedert (2018) includes poverty, insensitivity of people in power, rural neglect, corruption, unemployment and illiteracy. For purposes of this research the following ears were highlighted as key factors responsible for armed banditry escalation in northwest.

a- Weak of Security System: Security is a major concern of a country today. However, security is a freedom from danger, fear and anxiety. Poor security system in Nigeria particularly northwest region plays a vital role towards escalating insecurity that lead to banditry. Weak security is compliments to the alarming rate of banditry in northwest of region of Nigeria which may associated the access to lack of modern equipment for security operation across the country. According to Ogbuechi (2018) the police population ratio in Nigeria is 1:450 which fall below the standard set by the United Nations. This shows that inability of Nigerian police to combat crime effectively and criminality with rapid escalation of armed banditry and related violent activities such as kidnapping for ransom and highway robbery.

b- Wide Range of Under-Governed Spaces: Ungoverned spaces in Nigeria often refer to locations unreached by the government, hence becoming vulnerable to non-state armed groups (NSAGs). The unaddressed nature of Nigeria's ungoverned spaces is a breeding ground for underdevelopment and the spread of non-state armed actors.

The failure on the part of the state to impose order on its territory leaves much room for loosely organized vicious armed groups to wreak havoc on local communities in the northwest region. In the context of the ongoing banditry in the northwest geopolitical zone, the thesis of ungoverned spaces where territorial state control has been voluntarily or involuntarily ceded in whole or part to actors other than the relevant legally recognized sovereign authorities has been invoked to explain the rise and persistence of such criminal gangs and criminal activities (Ifeany, 2020).

Because banditry has been considered a problem of "ungoverned spaces" the federal government and state governments in the northwest region have largely employed military measures to curb it in addition to some ineffective nonmilitary measures addressing Nigeria's ungoverned spaces or preventing its spread must begin with proactive steps. Chukwuma and Mamuda (2021) argued that the revitalizing of the local government administration as an autonomous tier of government is necessary for re-establishing government presence in ungoverned spaces. Therefore, managing Nigeria's ungoverned spaces require a holistic, bottom-up approach to provide governance frameworks in the affected locations.

c- Fragile and Weak Border Management: Managing Nigeria's porous borders will also help to govern ungoverned spaces and monitor cross-border movements effectively. Illegal borders undermine a nation's effort to properly secure its territory and regulate the flow of people, goods and services. Nigeria and some of her West African neighbors suffer from the porosity of their borders. For four decades after ratifying the Protocol on Free Movement for the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and

related Protocol on transhumance, it has contributed to the indirect promotion of non-state violence. Therefore, it's time for Nigerian government to lead the call for a regional partnership for border security worldwide

Proliferation of Small Arms and Light Weapons: Another driving factor of banditry in northwestern Nigeria worthy of mentioning is the issue of arms proliferation. There has been an incremental influx of small arms and light weapons (SALWs) into Nigeria from the Sahel since the fall of Ghaddafi's regime in Libya (Adeoye, 2018). These arms and weapons end up in the hands of non-state actors like terrorists, militants and bandits, who use them to terrorize individuals and communities.

Furthermore, proliferation of heavy and lighter weapons in hand of non-security operatives in Nigeria leads to insecurity which cause harm, threats, anxiety and fear in the life citizen. The prevalence of these weapons is due to poor borders and lackadaisical attitude of security operatives in the borders of the country. The porosity of the Nigerian borders has aided the uncontrollable influx of migrants, mainly young men's from neighboring countries such as republic of Niger, Chad and republic of Benin responsible for some of the criminal acts (Schiling and Scheffran, 2012).

- d- **Socioeconomic Conditions:** Is one of the skyrocketing factors that wave the rising of banditry in Nigeria. The failure of Nigerian government to provide jobs and empowerments to youth to engage in meaningful activities gave room to social issues like banditry, armed robbery, kidnapping, cybercrime, terrorism and other relate offences arise and escalate widely. Siro (2014) affirmed that, the high level of poverty is a serious social problem comforting the country which seems endemic is becoming worrisome. It is worthy of note that states in the northwest region, especially Zamfara are specially endowed with large deposits of mineral resources like gold, gypsum, emerald, sapphire, lead, tourmaline, silver, barite, silica sand, granite, clay, and sandstones. It is estimated that "80% of mining in these areas is carried out illegally and on an artisanal basis, involving over two million people who depend on

illegal mining activities for survival (Maurice, 2020). The illegal miners in the region are mostly the poor and unemployed living in rural areas. The bandits profit from illegal mining by attacking villages and local communities where local artisanal miners live and carting away with gold and precious mineral resources (Timplehim, 2021). Revenues derived from the sale of stolen gold and precious mineral resources are used to purchase arms including motorcycles that are readily available in the region. With the presence of mineral and natural resources, armed bandits have incentives to continue their criminal activities, thereby rendering the conflict intractable (Ogbuechi 2018). In this sense, the concatenation of illegal mining and banditry produces a seemingly unending cycle of violence. For example, in early April 2019, the Nigerian government convinced that illegal mining drives banditry banned mining in Zamfara and other states in the northwest where mining activities are conducted. (Lackman, 2021). Most literature available socioeconomic conditions showing there is need to work toward the provision of socioeconomic goods education, healthcare, good roads and social amenities, youth employment, and equitable judicial services for pastoralist communities in the northwest geopolitical zone. Alao and Atere (2015) linked banditry and terrorism and other criminal acts to poverty unemployment. Although not all forms of criminal act could be linked to poverty, it has been contented that economic deprivation influences people drift in to illegal activities in other to meet their daily needs. In line with the above, Isyaku, Ishaq and Mukhtar (2018) opined that there is strong association between crimes and violence and high rate of poverty in Nigeria.

- e- Quick-money syndrome: Some Nigeria youth engage in different kind of criminal act such as cybercrime to harm individual banks account to withdraw money, arm robbery to attack on high ways to collect person's money and properties, kidnapping to collect ransom from the victim family and banditry to take away the cattle of people living in a community.

Impact of Armed Banditry on Security in Northwest Nigeria

The northwestern region has been experiencing many security challenges that led to thousands of deaths, loss of properties and displacements as a result of the rural banditry and cattle rustling, kidnapping and armed robbery in several communities. According to Abdullahi & Muktar (2022) armed banditry is an old security challenge in Nigeria, northwestern states in particular, and implies violent or nonviolent conditions that threaten the safety and security of the populace, state or state structures. While it is difficult to determine the exact number of armed bandits in the north-west, it has been estimated that about 30,000 bandits are associated with different gangs ranging from a few fighters to over 1,000 fighters operating in the region, and as result of the activities of non-state armed groups targeting the civilian population and its attendant security consequences, also there are more than 8.7 million people in need of immediate humanitarian assistance in the country (Brenner, 2021). Armed banditry constitutes a palpable security challenge in Northwestern Nigeria and Nigeria at large. Before the year 2010, banditry used to be overlooked and under-reported situations that were mostly handled by the locals. However, the year 2010 ushered in a set of criminal gangs who specialized in armed banditry and so a new style of banditry emerged which involved not only rustling the cattle but killing the owners and scaring people away from their communities (Rufa, 2017).

There are numerous security implications created by new armed banditry activities in the region, most important of these is undermined Nigeria's fragile national security. Bandit attacks on government entities, military bases, police stations, public office holders and their families, and host of citizens in the region have created a mammoth challenge for the state authorities. These also feed the flow of weapons on the hands of non-security personnel's, increasing ungoverned spaces problems as well as across borders' matters. Another significance effects of armed banditry is loss of human beings lives, according Osaghae, (2022) Armed bandits killed

8,300 people, including seven in Jigawa, 1,917 in Kaduna, 1,416 in Katsina, 202 in Kebbi, 644 in Sokoto, and 4,114 in Zamfara between January 2013 and March 2022. Some other source shows that more than 3,600 people were kidnapped, 8,000 were killed, and 200,000 were displaced due to the crisis in Zamfara alone. In addition, the region experienced over 1,000 kidnappings for ransom in 2021. In the same line The International Organization of Migration reported that armed groups engage in organized attacks that feature cattle-rustling, rape, looting, plundering, kidnapping, and murder. Between 2018 and 2020, at least 4,900 deaths were caused by armed banditry, which also generated hundreds of thousands of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in the north-west (IOM, 2022).

The effect of banditry is extensive, in addition to complicating the security crisis in the country, it has also increased the incidence of forced migration, food insecurity, cattle rustling, destruction of property, health challenges, displacement, humanitarian crises, and loss of people's lives. Likewise the impact of armed banditry on socio-economic life of the victims and the community in general, it was found that the impact was diverse and include disruption of farming and commercial activities, Psychological trauma suffered by victims and relatives of the victims of armed banditry, disruption of social activities such as school attendance and festivals. In other words, socio-economic activities in these communities have been disrupted.

New Trend of Armed Banditry in Northwest

To look deeply on current armed banditry activities in Northwest Nigeria, it's become quite necessary to consider the real empirical concept of armed banditry and other related criminal acts including kidnapping and armed robbery. For instance, Egwu (2015), in his work the "Political Economy of Rural Banditry in Contemporary Nigeria, viewed armed banditry as a practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders or the process of raiding of cattle from ranches. Although, in his opinion these activities was usually driven by several other means and factors, but, can be regarded generally as economically- based

form of criminality perpetuated through an informal network. In fact current armed banditry incidents in northwest region is not only the matter of stealing animals or process of raiding cattle from ranches. The phenomenon, become more serious, violent and quite challenge to the security operators and public in the area. ACAPS (2020) traced the upsurge of armed banditry in recent times from 2014 with cattle rustling activity and worsened in 2016 when bandits started killing local miners in Zamfara communities. The trend slowly spread to neighboring states of Katsina, Kaduna, Sokoto and Kebbi in 2019 and up to late 2022. The attacks by armed bandits have included shooting and killing, targeting traders, travelers, cattle rustling, kidnapping, rape, burning of entire village and looting of valuables, and more recently kidnapping famers for ransom. The most recent and popular acts of armed violence and rural banditry are characterized by armed robbery, Kidnapping cases in Nigeria has become so rampant and the country was ranked in the global index for worst countries to live in. It was further discovered that "kidnapping is a dreadful challenge that disrupts the tranquility and harmonious consolation of the country and has spread to nukes and crannies of Nigeria as a result of poverty and unemployment (Abdulkabir, 2017 p.5). Current armed banditry associated with armed robbery and kidnapping for ransom, cattle rustling which become quick money syndrome business. Moreover, its characterized by murder, rape, disturbing people's daily life activities and forcing civilians to displace are the most urgent national security concern in Nigeria and North-western states of Katsina, Sokoto, Kaduna, and Zamfara are the most directly affected by activities of armed bandits.

Kidnapping has now become a national epidemic (Campbell, 2018). Campbell further noted that "kidnapping has become a business, with whispers of involvement by politicians and the police as well as entrepreneurs in it, simply for the money. Kidnapping, cattle rustling and village raid, as in the cases of Kaduna, Zamfara and Katsina are the most affected states in the Northwest region (Attah, Sambo, Sule, Bello & Saragih, 2021). Available literature on current kidnapping cases

in the region reflecting dramatic change in the nature of historical practices of kidnapping known in the country. Kidnapping for ransom purposes, attacking highway travelers and traders with shooting and killing civilians in some cases, kidnapping farmers for ransom also one of the new trends of kidnapping. As Morgen (2020) reported on the kidnap-for-ransom economy in Nigeria notes that "between June 2011 and the end of March 2020, at least \$18.34 million has been paid to kidnappers as ransom. Even more frightening is that the larger proportion of that figure (just below \$11 million), was paid out between January 2016 and March 2020, indicating that kidnapping is becoming more lucrative. The bandits' victims are forced to pay between \$2,000 and \$20,000 for the release of captives. In more recent times, cases of armed robberies and abductions for ransom have become a major security challenge, and the Northwest region has been enmeshed in a rapid increase of rural banditry along its international boundaries and forested interior (Okoli & Ugwu, 2019). Another aspect of armed banditry is vast escalation of armed robbery cases in the region by targeting highway roads and rural communities to attack peoples and their properties.

Armed robbery is a crime which is occurred in different dimension in Nigeria which comprise high way robbery, property and car snatching in high ways, house, bank and market robberies etc. The kidnappers, robbers and cattle rustlers are often alternating their tactics with armed banditry that it is difficult for authority to label the act as cattle rustling, or kidnapping or banditry. Cattle rustlers is also another crime activity associated with armed banditry, it's become business for rustlers to attack cattle herders and making business which may cause the killing of cattle owners in many cases. The most disturbing trends here are that, in spite of the various states and federal government's strategies, measures and intervention to combat the armed banditry and related criminal acts, the level of banditry activities is increasing and continue to multiply day by day. Attempts at mitigating the problem became more cumbersome for the northwest states, the communities and an individuals affected and the country at large.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There are several factors that can explain the emergence and dramatically escalation of armed banditry and related criminal acts in north-west Nigeria including weak security system, wide range of under-Governed Spaces, fragile and weak border management, proliferation of small arms and lights weapons, quick money syndrome and socio-economic conditions(poverty and unemployment). The study concluded there are numerous security implications created by new armed banditry activities in the region, most important of these is undermined Nigeria's fragile national security, and increasing ungoverned spaces problems as well as across boarders' matter. Theses security consequences associated with other societal problems been created by armed banditry such as loss of human beings lives, food insecurity, cattle rustling, destruction of property, health challenges, displacement, humanitarian crises , displace of people and disruption of farming and commercial activities.

The nature of banditry activities has changed and become extremely violent and devastated recently with new trend and dimensions. Contemporary banditry has become more complicated and been brutal to the civilian who have been the target of banditries and associated with kidnapping for ransom, attacking highways users and rural communities especially farmers as well as cattle rustling. The strengthening of security system, effectiveness of adequate and modern equipment's for security sectors can prevent the escalation of banditry. Introducing new controlling borders measures to combat the flow of weapons with neighboring states and countries is highly recommended. Moreover, poverty eradications programs and providing more employments opportunities especially for youth will be one of the effective and sustainable strategies for addressing armed banditry and related criminal acts in northwest of the country.

REFERENCES

Abdulkabir, O. S. (2017). Causes and incisive solutions to the widespread of kidnapping in Nigeria current administration:

- Under scholastic scrutiny. *Journal of Political Sciences and Public Affairs*. 5(2), 23320761.
- Abdullahi & Mukhtar, (2022). African Journal of Sociological and Psychological Studies (AJOSAPS) ISSN 2752-6585 (online); ISSN 2752-6577 Volume 2, Number 1, June 2022
- Abdulyakeen, A. (2020). "Armed banditry and human security in Northwestern Nigeria: The impacts and the way forward", *Journal of Humanities, Social and Management Sciences*, 1(1), 89-107.
- ACAPS (2020). Banditry, Violence and Displacement in the North West. Retrieved from: <https://www.acaps.org/country/nigeria/crisis/northwest-banditry>.
- Adeoye, G. (2018). Bandits' attacks: Over 30 buried in Zamfara. The Punch, March 31st. Retrieved from: <https://punchng.com/bandits-attacks-over-30-buried-in-zamfara/>
- Alao, D. O., Atere, C. O. & Alao, O. (2015). Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria: The challenges and lessons. In Alao, D (ed), *Issues in conflict, peace and Government*. Ibadan: Fodnab Ventures.
- Ali Aḍo Siro (2014) Poverty Eradication In Northern Nigeria: An Assessment Of The Impact Of Nappes activities in Kano Metropolis *Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (JOSR-JHSS)* Volume 1, issue 8, Ver III (Aug.2014)
- Anka, S. A. (2018) Emerging Issues in Zamfara Armed Banditry and Cattle Rustling. <http://www.ijird.com>.
- Attah, N.E., Sambo, U., Sule, B. Bello, M.A. & Saḗagih, M.Y. (2021). "COVID 19 and increased security challenge in northern Nigeria: Interrogating armed banditry in northwestern Nigeria", *Journal of Religion, Social, Cultural and Political Sciences*, 6(1), 33-44. Retrieved from: <https://www.doi.org/10.33258/siasat.v6i1.87>
- Azeez, O., and Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, Bandits, and Violent Conflicts: understanding Cattle Rustling in Northern Nigeria. An article in *Africa Spectrum*, 51, 3, 99-105. German institute of

- Global and Area studies, Institute of African Affairs. Hamburg University Press.
- Bashir, M. (2014). Hopes for an end to cattle theft. *Daily Trust*, September 4th. Retrieved from: www.dailytrust.com.ng/daily/feature/33468-hopes-for-an-end-to-cattle-theft
- Brenner C, (2022), Combating Banditry in Northwest Nigeria. American Security Project, March 19, 2021; Campbell, John, "Not All Violent Problems Require Violent Solutions: Banditry in Nigeria's North-West," *Council on Foreign Relations* (2020).
- Burton, J. W. (1990) *Conflict Human Needs Theory*: New York: St. Martins Press.
- Campbell, J. (2018). Nigeria's National Kidnapping Crisis Is Expanding. Retrieved from
- Ceddert B, (2018). Economic Impact of Rural Banditry on Dansadau and Birnin Gwari Communities of Zamfara and Kaduna States. Centre for Democratic Development and Training, Zaria Research Report 2018.
- Chukwuma Okoli and Mamuda Abubakar, (2021), Crimelordism: Understanding a New Phenomenon in Armed Banditry in Nigeria, *Journal of Asian and African Studies* (2021).
- Egwu, S. (2015), The Political Economy of Rural Banditry in Contemporary Nigeria, In Kuna M. J. and Ibrahim, J. (eds) *Rural Banditry and Conflict in Northern Nigeria*. A Publication of Center for Democracy and Development.)
- Gupta, B. (2016). The political economy of rural banditry in contemporary Nigeria. In Kuna, M.J and Ibrahim, J (eds.). *Rural banditry and conflicts in northern Nigeria*, Abuja: Centre for Democracy and Development
- <http://www.cfr.org/blog/nigerias-national-kidnapping-crisis-expanding>
- Ifeanyi Onwuzu, (2020), Enclaves of Banditry: Ungoverned Forest Spaces and Cattle Rustling in Northern Nigeria, *African Studies Review* 64, no. 1 (2020).

- IOM, (2022), FLASH REPORT #86: Population Displacement North-west Nigeria: Zamfara State. International Organization for Migration, January 06-17, 2022.
- Isyaku, S. M., Ishaq, M. A. & Mukhtar, J. I. (2018). "A qualitative investigation into the factors responsible for *Boko Haram* insurgency: Study in Yobe State, Nigeria". *Jigawa Journal of Multi-disciplinary Studies*, 1 (1): 62-68.
- Kuna, M. J. & Ibrahim, J. (2015). *Rural banditry and conflict in northern Nigeria*. Centre of Democracy and Development, CITECT Estate Abuja.
- Lukman A (2021), Why FG banned mining activities in Zamfara, *International Center for Investigative Reporting (ICIR)*, March 2, 2021. <https://www.icirnigeria.org/why-fg-banned-mining-activities-in-zamfara/>.
- Maurice O, (2020), How illegal mining is driving local conflicts in Nigeria, *Institute for Security Studies*, June 16, 2020. <https://issafrica.org/iss-today/how-illegal-mining-is-driving-local-conflicts-in-nigeria>
- Morgen S.B,(2020) "Nigeria's Kidnap Problem: The Economics of the Kidnap Industry in Nigeria," *Morgen*, May 2020. https://www.sbmintel.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/202005_Nigeria-Kidnap.pdf
- National Bureau of Statistics (2017). *Statistical report on unemployment*. Retrieved from <http://nigerianstat.gov.ng/elibrary>.
- Ogbuechi, V.M. (2018). Kidnapping in Nigeria: The Way Forward. *Journal of Criminology and Forensic Studies*, Vol (3). Retrieved from <https://chembiopublishers.com/JOCFS180014.pdf>
- Okoli, A. C. & Ugwu, A. C. (2019). Of marauders and brigands: Scoping the threat of rural banditry in Nigeria's north west. *Brazilian Journal of African Studies*, 4(8), 201-2
- Olabanji, O. E. & Ese, U. (2014). Insecurity and socio-economic development in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 5(1), 40-63.

- Olaniyon, A. & Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, bandits, and violent conflicts: Understanding cattle rustling in northern Nigeria. *Africa Spectrum*, 51(3), 93-105.
- Osaghae E, (2021), *A History of Identities, Violence and Stability in Nigeria*, Vol. 6. (Oxford: Center for Research on Inequality, Human Security and Ethnicity, University of Oxford, 2021).
- Rotberg, R (2007). "Nigeria: elections and continuing challenges" in. Exploring the state of human insecurity in Nigeria: The root causes of the farmers-herdsmen conflict in Benue state and its manifestation on the livelihood of rural farmers and pastoralists. *ADRRRI Journal of Arts and Social Science*, 16(6), 60-98. *You need to know about Africa and why it matters*. New York: Brookings.
- Rufai, M. A. (2017). "Shadow actors behind cattle rustling and rural banditry in Zamfara State". *Dege Journal of the Faculty of Arts and Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS), Nigeria*. 1(2): 11-
- Schilling, J. Opiyo, E.O. and Scheffran, J. (2012). Raiding Pastoral Livelihoods: Motives and Effect of Violent Conflict in North-western Kenya: A Springer open journal
- Timilehin A, (2021), Banditry: Questions as govt confirms miners fund criminals terrorizing Nigerians, *Daily Post*, March 16, 2021. <https://dailypost.ng/2021/03/18/banditry-questions-as-govt-confirms-miners-fund-criminals-terrorizing-nigerians/>